

METHODS OF WORD FORMATION IN ENGLISH (MORPHOLOGICAL METHOD, SEMANTIC METHOD, COMPOSITION METHOD)

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Abstract: *This article provides information about English word formation and word formation, as well as grammatical and syntactic construction.*

Key words: *Paradigmatic morphology, syntagmatic morphology, syntax, grammar, morpheme, lexeme.*

Grammar consists of two main sections: morphology and syntax. According to the way these elements are studied (paradigmatic and syntagmatic), the following 4 classifications can be seen:

1. Paradigmatic morphology
2. Syntagmatic morphology
3. Paradigmatic syntax
4. Syntagmatic syntax

Here, paradigmatic morphology and syntagmatic syntax do not require an explanation, but by syntagmatic morphology we mean phrases in the order of noun+noun, adjective+noun, verb+adverb, and by paradigmatic syntax we mean the variants of a certain sentence. held: I speak English. I don't speak English. Do I speak English? I have spoken English. I haven't spoken English. Morphology is

derived from the Greek words morphē - form and logos - teaching, and studies the morphological structure of words, the relationship of morphemes to each other in the formation of grammatical forms, the laws of arrangement, mutual oppositions of paradigm-forming forms, word groups and their meaning. More precisely, it is a grammatical theory of words, that is, a department that studies the paradigmatics of language elements. One of the main conditions for dividing the language into elements is that each element has its own unit

to have. The unity of morphology is the smallest meaning in speech activity is a meaningful element. Appearance of this element in speech is morph and appearance in language

called a morpheme. For example, the English word fishers has three meanings unsur, i.e. fish - er - s, translated into Uzbek as "fishermen".

will be done.

A morpheme is the smallest meaningful linguistic unit that makes up a word.

For example: writers. basic lexical meaning 2) noun forming suffix 3) plural forming suffix. Common morpheme in English is word (word), affixal (bound) and free (free). divided into morphemes. But it should be noted that in our example aboveer and -s morphemes are homonyms. From this point of view, morphemes are considered as stem, i.e. it is divided into zero (zero) morpheme and homonymous morpheme. Phoneme is the smallest meaningless unit of the language (tale-table; boy-ax). In morphology, grammatical categories of word groups are determined as a result of the paradigmatic status of the morpheme system. For example, if we look at the paradigm of nouns, it is possible to show the categories of number and agreement from its grammatical categories. Word and morpheme. As we know, morphology is a branch of grammar that deals with word forms. A word is the largest unit of morphology that can perform a syntactic

function. Speaking of words and morphemes, a morpheme is the smallest unit of meaning. However, in this case, by meaning, we should understand not the lexical semantic meaning, but the grammatical meaning.

A word is independent of the language, conveys certain meanings, emotions, is a phonetically and grammatically formed, complete unit. The fact that a word has a complete structure, individuality, is a part of a sentence arrival shows its difference from a morpheme. Morphemes, phonemes and words combine with each other in different ways. Their combination is subject to certain linguistic laws. Regardless of the size or smallness of the linguistic units, the method of their syntagmatic arrangement in the speech process, the order of use, the sum, that is, the connection of the element used in one case with the second case is called distribution. Distribution comes into contact with all levels of the language hierarchy. Morphological and syntactic distribution studies the relationships of the smallest units (phonemes) in the language, phonological distribution, morphemes and the features of word placement in the context. The use of the distributive method in morphology depends on the process of dividing the language system into morphological segments. The distinction between morphology and syntax is closely related to how we understand word boundaries. In general, morphology is a branch of grammar that deals with word forms. Syntax, on the other hand, is a part of grammar, and vocabulary deals with phrases and sentences.

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